

BRAND LOVE: EXPLORING RELATIONSHIPS WITH ENVIRONMENT, SOCIAL, GOVERNANCE (E.S.G.) AND BRAND PURPOSE

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

The advancing concept of **Brand Love** has received a lot of attention from managers as well as from academicians (Batra et al., 2012). Organizations are particularly concerned to understand the notion (Palusuk et al., 2019), as liking and satisfaction from consumer side towards a brand are not sufficient to build a long-term customer-brand relationship (Jones & Sasser, 1995). According to Fournier (1998) the principal element of customer-brand relationship is love, which is further cultivated with live cases by Roberts (2004) in his book 'Lovemarks'.

Research implies that love towards an object is possible when a consumer purchases an object, engages with it, and expresses the thoughts and feelings toward the object to make it distinct than other brands of similar nature while also linking it as having human like aspects (Palusuk & Kitchen, 2015). Largely, consumer expresses the attachment as the brand represents them and such emotional attachment is elaborated as to be a long-term relationship rather than a short span affection-based emotion (Batra et al., 2012).

Understanding such attachment and its outcomes is of crucial importance for brands in emerging markets, where managers critically depend on various one-sided communication stunts such as, social interactive engagement led by social influencers rather than user generated content, which proves to be more effective (Welbourne & Grant, 2015). Thus, this investigation leads to practical contributions for brand managers and for academic researchers seeking to explore customer-brand relationships, specifically brand love.

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

This study aims to comprehend the role of E.S.G on brand love, while brand trust mediates the relationship, and brand self-integration is an important moderator. The effect on brand love for brands with and without brand purpose is considered as well. Three key consequences of brand love i.e., resistance to negative information, eWOM, and non-willingness to switch are also considered. Grounded on the literature review, research objectives, research questions, and theoretical insights, the following conceptual framework with the significant consequences of brand love is shown in Figure – 1.

Figure 2. Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework pictorially synthesizes the connection between E.S.G as an important independent variable, on brand love. Alongside, the model proposes to evaluate vital constructs as mediator and moderator. Brand self-integration moderates the effect of E.S.G on brand love. The research model is proposed to also examine the positive role of E.S.G while investigating the mediating effect of brand trust, while authenticity moderates the relationship on how brand love can be elicited among consumers. The hypothesis from hypothesis 1 (H1) through hypothesis 9 (H9) are labelled.

This study is based on the quantitative research to examine the relationship between brand love and E.S.G among the millennial generational cohort consumers in Nepal who use various FMCG and service brands. The role of brand purpose as a control variable is also embraced in this study. The respondents were selected if they were born within 1977 – 2000 (Shin, Eastman, & Mothersbaugh, 2017) and fall in the age group of 22 to 45 years of age by asking them prior to handing

over a copy of the request letter as a way of screening they fit the respondent age cohort.

FINDINGS

The data analysis was completed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). After an initial data screening process, 334 responses were valid out of 391. Reliability analysis was carried out and one of the items had to be dropped for the scale - willingness to switch to competing brand to ensure the reliability score fit above 0.7. Thereon, SEM's measurement model was obtained as shown in Figure 2 and goodness of fit was tested and fulfilled.

Figure 2. Measurement Model

The path analysis was carried out and the structural model is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Structural Model

The statistical results are presented in Table 3.

Table 1: Statistical Results

Hypotheses	Hypothesized Paths	Path Coefficients	P-Value	Test Result
H1a	ENVIRONMENTAL \longrightarrow BRAND LOVE	0.426	***	Supported
H1b	SOCIAL \longrightarrow BRAND LOVE	0.755	***	Supported
H1c	GOVERNANCE \longrightarrow BRAND LOVE	0.520	***	Supported
H2a	ENVIRONMENTAL x BRAND SELF INTEGRATION \longrightarrow BRAND LOVE	-0.055	0.001	Supported
H2b	SOCIAL x BRAND SELF INTEGRATION \longrightarrow BRAND LOVE	-0.122	***	Supported
H2c	GOVERNANCE x BRAND SELF INTEGRATION \longrightarrow BRAND LOVE	0.037	.233	Not Supported
H3a	ENVIRONMENTAL \longrightarrow TRUST	0.433	***	Supported

H3b	SOCIAL \longrightarrow TRUST	0.012	0.863	Not Supported
H3c	GOVERNANCE \longrightarrow TRUST	-0.211	***	Supported
H4	TRUST \longrightarrow BRAND LOVE	0.02	0.916	Not Supported
H5a	ENVIRONMENTAL x BRAND AUTHENTICITY \longrightarrow TRUST	-0.078	.024	Supported
H5b	SOCIAL x BRAND AUTHENTICITY TRUST \longrightarrow	-0.044	.414	Not Supported
H5c	GOVERNANCE x BRAND AUTHENTICITY \longrightarrow TRUST	-0.173	.003	Supported
H6	BRAND LOVE \longrightarrow eWOM	0.830	***	Supported
H7	BRAND LOVE \longrightarrow Resistance to negative information	0.895	***	Supported
H8	BRAND LOVE \longrightarrow Non-willingness to switch to another brand	0.644	***	Supported
H9a	Brands with Purpose - Environment	0.398	***	Supported
H9b	Brands with Purpose - Social	0.330	***	Supported
H9c	Brands with Purpose - Governance	0.195	***	Supported

ORIGINALITY/VALUE

This study's objective is to provide an understanding of the relationships between E.S.G and brand love and identifying the effects of moderating and mediating variables. The research question was stated as "What is the effect on millennial consumer's perception of a company's environmental, social and governance (E.S.G) practices on their brand love?" A quantitative research approach was carried forward to find answers to the research questions. With questionnaires being the primary tool for research, data collection from millennial generational cohort of Nepalese consumers was carried out and SEM was employed for analysis purpose.

DISCUSSION/CONCLUSION

This study was initiated as an exploratory one after careful review of existing literature and their research gaps. Similarly, the present study too has certain limitations and paves way for future research potential. Although this study has significant value in academic as well as practice as have other research, there are some limitations it poses. Firstly, generalizability of the results due to demographic characteristics and geography of the respondents must be considered. The generational cohort considered as suitable were millennials only as well. Future research is encouraged to consider larger sample size along with mix of generational cohorts and other segmenting factors like location and income levels.

Similarly, researchers may employ different data collection and analysis tools and techniques in the future by using qualitative approaches and interviews as a data collection tool as well to further explore the key constructs that are in a development stage. A case on specific brand might also provide more insights regarding brand love and E.S.G activities. Thus, there is a strong gap in existing research on the emerging topic of brand purpose. In this research, brand purpose was measured based on information available on company websites and media. It would be interesting to include measure of brand purpose attributes like purpose alignment, purpose customers awareness or purpose emotional connection and to identify the contribution of these attributes on E.S.G customers' perception.

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